

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

ANNUAL REPORT 2015–2016

CONTENTS

Message from the President	1
Milestones	2
By the Numbers	3
Program Highlights	5
Affiliates	17
Publications	19
Resources and Fiscal Management	20
Board of Directors and Advisory Groups	22
Staff and Presidential Fellows	23
Sponsors and Funders	24

The Council on Library and Information Resources (CLIR) is an independent, nonprofit organization that forges strategies to enhance research, teaching, and learning environments in collaboration with libraries, cultural institutions, and communities of higher learning. CLIR aspires to transform the information landscape to support the advancement of knowledge.

CLIR promotes forward-looking collaborative solutions that transcend disciplinary, institutional, professional, and geographic boundaries in support of the public good. In pursuing its mission, CLIR is committed to building trust, retaining independence, fostering collaboration, cultivating effective leadership, and capitalizing on strategic opportunities.

MESSAGE from the PRESIDENT

Charles Henry, *President*

May 2016 marked the 60th anniversary of CLIR's founding as the Council on Library Resources (CLR). Over six decades, our projects and programs have evolved with a remarkable continuity of mission and focus. CLIR's founders held that collective action and collaborative processes were necessary to resolve the looming complexities of academic information in the mid 1950s, which included multi-institutional collection sharing, large-scale preservation of deteriorating resources, and methods to manage the proliferation of new media as an aspect of cultural curation.

Today we grapple with many of these same challenges, but in a markedly different environment. While CLIR's founding vision continues to animate our programs, the organization has evolved in important ways:

—Expanding our role in exploring and promoting digital technology as a transformational means of organizing academic knowledge. DLF exemplifies that impulse and continues to grow.

—Significantly increasing geographical reach. Our collaborative ventures, award and fellowship recipients, Board members, and advisors span the planet.

—Diversifying collaborators. While CLR's original focus was on academic libraries, our constituencies today include archives, museums, historical societies, and national and international digital projects.

—Adopting social justice as a tenet of our mission. We believe that all digital libraries and projects must strive to increase our capacity to understand our world and ourselves, acknowledge the regenerative properties of an honest question, and insist that knowledge be accessible and open to all, while celebrating the sweep and depth of human curiosity.

This year's annual report provides abundant evidence of this evolution. We are deeply grateful to our sponsors and funders for their continued support of our work. On this anniversary, we also acknowledge our debt to CLIR's visionary founders while working for those generations hence who will inherit our best intentions.

Charles Henry, March 2017

MILESTONES

1956 CLR incorporated; establishes office in Washington, DC, and holds first board of directors meeting. Within first year awards more than \$120,000 in grants.

1957 Funds investigations of W. J. Barrow at the Virginia State Library into the causes of paper deterioration.

1957 Funds University of Virginia project to demonstrate the feasibility of using closed-circuit TV between libraries for resource sharing.

1959 Funds AVCO Manufacturing Corporation project to develop Verac, a micro-reduction system that stores a million pages in a cubic foot of space.

1961 Sponsors first International Conference of Cataloguing Principles in Paris. Hosted by the International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA), the meeting was a major step toward the international standardization of cataloging.

1961 Establishes King Committee to study ways to improve the Library of Congress through automation. Committee urges creation of a standard for conversion of bibliographic data information to machine-readable form.

1962 Funds team at MIT headed by J. C. R. Licklider to develop a series of reports on libraries of the future. Exhibits of future libraries with automated features were presented at world fairs in Seattle in 1962 and New York in 1964–1965.

This led to the adoption of MARC as a bibliographic standard in 1968.

1971 Funds Ohio Colleges Library Center project to develop an online union catalog with shared cataloging capability that emerges as the nation's first bibliographic utility.

1971 Funds IFLA project to strengthen administrative operations so it can transition from a European organization to a truly international library organization.

1972 Funds National Serials Data Program, located at the Library of Congress, which produces a national machine-readable database for serials that permits uniform transfer of data on serial publications.

1973 Establishes Academic Library Management Intern Program, designed to assist in the development of managers for the nation's large research and academic libraries.

1979 Establishes the Bibliographic Services Development Program to develop a nationally acceptable strategy for acquiring and sharing bibliographic control over resources available to users of the nation's libraries.

1979 Funds American Council of Learned Societies (ACLS) project to undertake a study of scholarly communication, resulting in *Scholarly Communication: Report on the National Enquiry*.

1984 Funds ACLS project to establish an Office of Scholarly Communication and Technology.

1984 Funds IFLA project to create core programs in preservation, transborder data flow, and development of international MARC.

1984 Establishes Committee on Preservation and Access to undertake a national planning effort leading to the development of an independent body, the Commission on Preservation and Access (CPA), in 1986.

1987 Funds production of *Slow Fires: On the Preservation of the Human Record*, a film by Terry Sanders, which tells the story of the global crisis in preserving library materials.

1995 Spearheads organizational planning for the National Digital Library Federation (NDLF). NDLF changes name to Digital Library Federation in 1997 and becomes a formal program of CLIR.

1997
CPA and CLR
join to create
CLIR

BY the NUMBERS

More than **\$47 million** given in grants, scholarships, and fellowships

More than **195 institutions** awarded grants

184 CLIR sponsors in the USA, Canada, and overseas

Since
1997

In
2016

862 individuals awarded scholarships or fellowships

105 reports published in print and on the Web

135 DLF members in the USA, Canada, and overseas

Shading represents distribution of sponsors and members by state. Darker shading indicates greater numbers.

CLIR works with academic, learning, and cultural institutions; scholars; specialists; and practitioners dedicated to building a rich and coherent information environment to advance knowledge. We believe that the future of learning and the advancement of knowledge depend on the preservation, organization, and accessibility of information. To this end, we invest in intellectual leadership, professional development, and strategic programs.

PROGRAM HIGHLIGHTS

July 1, 2015–June 30, 2016

Digital Library Federation

The Digital Library Federation (DLF) is a robust, diverse, and inclusive community of practitioners who advance research, learning, social justice, and the public good through the creative design and wise application of digital library technologies. DLF serves as a resource and catalyst for collaboration among its institutional members, and among all who are invested in the success of libraries, museums, and archives in the digital age. As an action-oriented CLIR program, DLF connects the broad vision of CLIR's research to the pragmatic efforts of a vibrant practitioner community.

The **DLF Forum**, an annual event, serves as a venue for exchanging information that will lead to a better understanding of the elements and complexity of digital library evolution, as well as for launching new collaborative and practical work. The 2015 Forum, held in Vancouver in November, was the first to take place outside the United States. Drawing some 600 attendees, the largest number to date, the Forum focused not just on the “how” of digital library technologies, but also on the “why”—the social, political, and ethical contexts of the library and information professions.

The first DLF Liberal Arts College Preconference was held in conjunction with the 2015 Forum. The one-day meeting was designed to foster conversation and build community among those who work with digital libraries or digital scholarship at liberal arts colleges. The preconference included concurrent sessions of presentations and panels on pedagogical, organizational, and technological approaches to digital humanities and digital scholarship, data curation, digital collections, and digital preservation.

Keynote speaker Safiya Noble, above, addresses the 2015 DLF Forum audience, below, on “Power, Privilege, and the Imperative to Act.”

2016 DLF eResearch Network Institutional Participants

Bucknell University
Carnegie Mellon University
The Claremont Colleges
Drexel University
Iowa State University
Los Alamos National Laboratory
Macalester College
Middlebury College
National Institutes of Health
New York University
Rice University
University at Albany, SUNY
University of California, Berkeley
University of Chicago
University of Guelph
University of Iowa
University of Ottawa
University of Pennsylvania
University of Washington

Interest groups help practitioners in the DLF community work across institutional lines. They include, among others, the Born-Digital Access Group, DLF Digital Library Pedagogy Group, DLF Project Managers Group, and the DLF Assessment Interest Group (AIG). The AIG works to measure the impact of digital collections and costs of digitization; develop effective benchmarks for measuring collections across platforms; understand cultural factors that influence digital library development; and explore how best to gather, analyze, communicate, and share such information effectively with librarians, scholars, and administrators. In 2015–2016, the AIG redesigned its powerful digitization cost calculator that runs on community-contributed data. This tool is one part of a planned “assessment dashboard” addressing a range of digital library needs.

DLF fosters participation and interdisciplinary connections with other professional and conference communities through several **grants and fellowships**, including tuition grants to the Digital Humanities Summer Institute, DLF Forum Fellowships, and reciprocal Cross-Pollinator Travel Grants organized with a dozen organizations in cultural heritage and scholarly communication. In 2015–2016, DLF made 17 awards.

In November 2015, DLF partnered with the Association of Moving Image Archivists (AMIA) in sponsoring the third annual **DLF/AMIA Hack Day** in Portland, OR. These Hack Days are unique opportunities for practitioners and managers of digital audiovisual collections to join with digital library developers and engineers for an intense day of collaboration to develop solutions for audiovisual preservation and access.

On January 1, 2016, the **National Digital Stewardship Alliance (NDSA)**, a consortium of organizations committed to the long-term preservation of digital information, moved its administrative home from the Library of Congress to DLF (see p. 17).

Below: 2015 AMIA + DLF Cross-Pollinator Cora Johnson-Roberson, right, worked with Kathryn Gronsbell, left, and Michelle Roell, center, on programming at 2015 Hack Day. Photo: Snowden Becker.

DIGITIZATION COST CALCULATOR

dashboard.diglib.org

Digitizing Hidden Special Collections and Archives

CLIR's Digitizing Hidden Special Collections and Archives program is a national competition that funds the digitization of unique and rare collections for the benefit of scholars and the general public.

Digitizing Hidden Special Collections and Archives seeks to enhance the emerging global digital research environment in ways that support new kinds of scholarship for the long term, ensuring that the full wealth of resources held by institutions of cultural memory becomes integrated with the open Web. By emphasizing the values of scholarly significance, collaboration, comprehensive coverage, connectedness, sustainability, and openness, CLIR aims to promote broad access, careful preservation, attention to usability, inclusion, and an awareness of current best practices in the digitization of special collections. By encouraging strategic collaboration and communication among this program's grant recipients, CLIR expects to help increase understanding of the complex factors informing digitization strategies in the professional communities responsible for rare and unique collections.

In January 2016, CLIR announced the first group of awardees for the Digitizing Hidden Special Collections and Archives competition, which is supported by a generous grant from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation.

The inaugural round of Digitizing Hidden Special Collections funded **18 projects** at **47 institutions** with grants totalling **\$3.94 million**

Documenting Our Melting Past

How have our polar regions changed in the last century? Archives and historical collections provide us with evidence before digitally recorded data became the norm. The National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC) at the University of Colorado Boulder houses a collection of historical archival photographs that record the earth's glaciated regions. The collection comprises repeat photographs of the same glacier, taken from the same vantage point and at the same time of year, but taken many years apart.

With funding from CLIR, NSIDC and the UC Boulder Libraries are digitizing the entirety of the archive's print glacier photograph collection. Digital images and associated metadata will be provided in two digital platforms—one of which is co-discoverable with born-digital cryospheric data, the other of which is co-discoverable with collections more likely to reach humanists and social scientists.

The NSIDC's records reveal how unusual the past century's changes are and document the first stages of change. Digitizing these records gives access to reusable data that can prompt further investigation of environmental science.

Photos of Okpilak Glacier taken in 1907 and 2004 show the dramatic recession of the glacial field in less than a century. *Top photo: Ernest Leffingwell; bottom photo: Matt Nolan. National Snow and Ice Data Center, compiler. 2002, updated 2015. Glacier Photograph Collection. Boulder, Colorado, USA. National Snow and Ice Data Center. Available at <http://dx.doi.org/10.7265/N5/NSIDC-GPC-2009-12>.*

Saving PBS NewsHour Broadcasts

With a Digitizing Hidden Collections grant, The American Archive of Public Broadcasting is managing the digitization of 32 years of daily broadcast news programs from 1975 to 2007 chronicling national and worldwide news and cultural affairs. Programs include *The Robert MacNeil Report*, *The MacNeil Lehrer Report*, *The MacNeil/Lehrer NewsHour*,

and *The NewsHour with Jim Lehrer*. Many programs exist on obsolete video formats of 2", 1", and Beta. The project will digitize, preserve, and allow public access to some 7,512 programs through the American Archive of Public Broadcasting. More than 9,000 existing transcripts for the entire 40 years (1975–present) will also be made available.

2015 Digitizing Hidden Special Collections and Archives Awards

"All Day Singing": Preserving and Providing Access to Original Early Twentieth Century Field Recordings in the Frank Clyde Brown Collection, \$74,595
Duke University Libraries

Bibliotheca Philadelphiensis: Toward a Comprehensive Online Library of Medieval and Early Modern Manuscripts in PACSCL Libraries in Eastern Pennsylvania and Delaware, \$499,086
Lehigh University, Linderman Library; Free Library of Philadelphia; University of Pennsylvania Libraries; Bryn Mawr College; College of Physicians of Philadelphia; Haverford College; Library Company of Philadelphia; Rosenbach Museum and Library; Swarthmore College; Temple University; University of Delaware; Chemical Heritage Foundation; Franklin & Marshall College; Villanova University; Philadelphia Museum of Art

Biodiversity Heritage Library Field Notes Project, \$491,713
Smithsonian Institution; Missouri Botanical Garden, Peter H. Raven Library; American Museum of Natural History; Yale Peabody Museum; Harvard University, Herbaria Botany Libraries; Harvard Museum of Comparative Zoology, Ernst Mayr Library; University of California, Berkeley Museum of Vertebrate Zoology; New York Botanical Garden, LuEsther T. Mertz Library; The Field Museum; Internet Archive

The Digital Archive of Native American Petitions in Massachusetts, \$275,795
Harvard University, Yale University

Digitizing British Manuscripts at UCLA's Clark Library, 1601–1800, \$194,225
University of California, Los Angeles

Digitizing Over Fifty Years of Jukebox Music News: Cash Box, 1942–1996, \$60,214
College of William & Mary, Earl Gregg Swem Library

The Edison Collection of American Sheet Music, 1800–1870, \$243,682
University of Michigan

"I thought there was nothing so glorious as war...": Creating Online Access to the World War I Materials at The Museum of Flight, \$58,200
The Museum of Flight

New England's Hidden Histories: Providing Public Access to the Manuscripts of New England's First Churches, Incubators of American Democracy, \$210,000
American Congregational Association, Phillips Library, Connecticut Conference of the United Church of Christ, New England Historic and Genealogical Society

PBS NewsHour Digitization Project, \$500,000
WGBH Educational Foundation, Library of Congress, Greater Washington Educational Telecommunications Association (WETA)

Photographic Collections of the Erie Canal, \$59,100
Erie Canal Museum, Canal Society of New York State

Revealing Our Melting Past: Toward a Digital Library of Historic Glacier Photography, \$148,586
University of Colorado

Revealing Visual Culture: Digitizing Modern Illustrated Periodical Tear Sheets in the Walt Reed Illustration Archive, \$250,000
Washington University in St. Louis

Sharing "Gabo" with the World: Building the Gabriel Garcia Marquez Online Archive from His Papers at the Harry Ransom Center, \$126,730
The Harry Ransom Center at The University of Texas at Austin

The Road from Hell Is Paved with Little Rocks: Digitizing the History of Segregation and Integration of Arkansas's Educational System, \$106,908
University of Arkansas at Little Rock, Center for Arkansas History and Culture; Central Arkansas Library System Butler Center for Arkansas Studies; Little Rock Central High School National Historic Site

UMN Libraries/Umbra African American Digital Collection: Digitizing African American Archival Materials Across University of Minnesota Collections, \$224,450
University of Minnesota

Voices of the Revolution: Digitizing 30,000 French Pamphlets from the Newberry Library, \$219,999
Newberry Library

YWCA of the USA Digitization and Access Project, \$250,000
Smith College

For more details, visit <https://www.clir.org/hiddencollections/awards/for-2015>.

Since 2004, the program has placed **153 fellows** at **68 host institutions** across the United States and Canada

Saving Software to Save Data

Describing, preserving, and sharing data have become common, but the software tools, parameters, and workflows used to extract knowledge from those data are not usually well curated. This hinders the ability of others to extend or replicate the work, a cornerstone of the scientific process.

Postdoctoral Fellow **Fernando Rios** is working with a team at Johns Hopkins University to develop a strategy for archiving and sharing research software that is now being piloted at the university. He has also created a toolbox for curating and archiving research software that helps research data management specialists address potential knowledge gaps in providing software archiving or preservation services as a companion to data services.

Postdoctoral Fellowship Program

CLIR's Postdoctoral Fellowship Program offers recent Ph.D. graduates opportunities to work on projects in the digital environment that strengthen connections between library collections and current research.

CLIR Postdoctoral Fellows are tackling massive systemic challenges facing the future of scholarly information resources, whether building capacity for digital humanities research support, inculcating responsible data management practices, or developing more usable and sustainable digital libraries. The program cultivates new leaders by giving highly skilled and articulate individuals broad exposure to issues facing cultural heritage institutions, practical opportunities to learn, and connections within the profession and beyond.

Launched in 2004 as CLIR Postdoctoral Fellowships in Scholarly and Information Resources, the program has expanded significantly with a focus on data curation across disciplines in the humanities, social sciences, and sciences. Fellows are embedded in libraries, data curation centers, and other research support units to develop sustainable approaches to research data management that transcend institutional, national, and disciplinary boundaries. Since 2012, with grants from the Mellon and Sloan foundations, CLIR and its Digital Library Federation have supported **58 fellowships in data curation** in the social sciences and sciences, software curation, medieval studies, visual studies, and early modern studies at 41 host institutions in the United States and Canada. In June 2016, CLIR announced new data curation fellowships for Latin American and Caribbean studies.

Since 2013, with funds from the Mellon Foundation, CLIR has supported **microgrant projects** for data curation fellows to conduct collaborative research addressing problems shared across institutions. Fellows develop microgrant ideas with colleagues in the fellowship, with input from scholars and experts in relevant areas. Recent projects include The Digital Canvas, an online hub for resources related to the study of digital art history, and Reading Cities, a digitally augmented text platform serving teachers and researchers of texts and urban environments.

To mark the program's first decade, current and former fellows worked together writing essays on current issues affecting research collections and services in the context of higher education. *The Process of Discovery: The CLIR Postdoctoral Fellowship Program and Future of the Academy*, published in September 2015, addresses the nature of collaboration, the changing and expanding role of the library, the future of data management in libraries, and alternative academic career paths.

Facing page, left to right: Laura Aydelotte, Alberto Campagnolo, Mary Lindsay Van Tine.

2016 Postdoctoral Fellows

New Fellows

Yasmin AlNoamany

Computer Science, Old Dominion University
Host: University of California, Berkeley

John Borghi

Integrative Neuroscience, Stony Brook University
Host: California Digital Library, University of California

Paul Broyles

English, University of Virginia
Host: North Carolina State University

Alberto Campagnolo

Digital Humanities, University of the Arts, London
Host: Library of Congress

Alexandra Chassanoff

Information and Library Science, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Host: Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Erin Connolly

Medieval English, University of Nottingham
Host: University of Pennsylvania

Thomas Cook

Political Science, University of Colorado
Host: Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City

Kristy Golubiewski-Davis

Anthropology, University of Minnesota
Host: Middlebury College

Jennifer Grayburn

History of Art and Architecture, University of Virginia
Host: Temple University

Veronica Ikeshoji-Orlati

Classical Art and Archaeology, University of Virginia
Host: Vanderbilt University

Michaela Kelly

Cultural Anthropology, University of Tokyo
Host: Lafayette College

Bommae Kim

Quantitative Psychology, University of Virginia
Host: Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City

Jacob Levernier

Psychology, University of Oregon
Host: University of Pennsylvania

Zack Lischer-Katz

Communication and Information, Rutgers University
Host: University of Oklahoma

Elizabeth Parke

East Asian Studies, University of Toronto
Host: University of Toronto

Jacqueline Quinless

Sociology, University of Victoria
Host: University of Victoria

Mara Sedlins

Social Psychology, University of Washington
Host: Duke University

Mason Scott Thompson

Anthropology, Arizona State University
Host: U.S. Agency for International Development

Katherine Thornton

Information Science, University of Washington
Host: Yale University

Loren Valterza

Italian Medieval Literature, Rutgers University
Host: University of Notre Dame

Heather Wach

Medieval History, University of Iowa
Host: University of Wisconsin-Madison

Jeffrey Wayno

History, Columbia University
Host: Columbia University

Iskandar Zulkarnain

Visual and Cultural Studies, University of Rochester
Host: University of Rochester

Continuing Fellows as of June 30, 2016

Jacquelyn Clements

History of Art, Johns Hopkins University
Host: University of Toronto

Dimitrios Latsis

Film Studies, University of Iowa
Host: Internet Archive

Chreston Miller

Computer Science and Applications, Virginia Tech
Host: Virginia Tech

Fernando Rios

Geography, University of Buffalo, SUNY
Host: Johns Hopkins University

Edward Triplett

History of Art and Architecture, University of Virginia
Host: Duke University

Martin Tsang

Anthropology, Florida International University
Host: University of Miami

Mary Lindsay Van Tine

English and Comparative Literature, Columbia University
Host: Swarthmore College/University of Pennsylvania

Qian Zhang

Physical Oceanography, Louisiana State University
Host: University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Leading Change Institute

The Leading Change Institute (LCI), a joint effort of CLIR and EDUCAUSE and successor to the Frye Leadership Institute, aims to prepare the next generation of leaders in libraries, information services, and higher education by engaging those who seek to further develop their skills for the benefit of higher education.

Higher education requires leaders, particularly in the information sector, who can inspire, advocate for, and advance needed change. Participants in the LCI learn how to create a collaborative community that takes leadership on critical issues. They develop the skills to build public will, set an agenda for change, and advocate for needed reform. They learn by doing through engagement with real-world issues.

Thirty-nine individuals attended the 2016 Institute held June 12–17 in Washington, DC. The curriculum for this year's LCI, as for previous years, was informed by key challenges in higher education, including new sources of competition; use of technology to support effective teaching and learning; distance learning; changing modes of scholarly communication; an increasing focus on students; and, fundamentally, a transformation in the qualities necessary for leadership in today's increasingly ambiguous and rapidly changing environment.

Participants, deans, and speakers discussed approaches to addressing these challenges. They exchanged ideas for collaboration, collective creativity, and innovation within and across departments, institutions, and local or regional boundaries, and they explored the importance of community mentorship and advocacy.

Following the Institute, participants are invited to join an alumni-wide listserv and to take part in a monthly in-person conversation.

To date, the program has graduated **678 alumni** from a broad range of domestic and international institutions of higher learning

Leading Change Institute Participants 2016

Paul Allison, Duquesne University
Andrew Amrhein, Harvard Business School
Sucharitha Bachanna, West Virginia University
Lisa Baker, University of Miami, Coral Gables
Brandon Bernier, University of Wisconsin-Madison
Beth Bohstedt, Hamilton College
Jennifer Bowen, University of Rochester
Kyle Bowen, The Pennsylvania State University
Kellie Campbell, Saint Michael's College
Gary Chinn, The Pennsylvania State University
Annie Downey, Reed College
Mohamed El Ouiridi, Duke University
Sarah Evelyn, Brown University

Jody Fagan, James Madison University
Matthew Gardzina, Bucknell University
Kevin Garewal, University of Akron
Gayleen Gray, University of Guelph
Elizabeth Gushee, Harry Ransom Center, The University of Texas at Austin
Edward Hudson, California State University, Office of the Chancellor
Cintha Ippoliti, Oklahoma State University
Lisa Kahle, State University of New York at Cortland
Debralee Krahmer, Colgate University
Kristen Lukens, St. Norbert College
Valerie Lynn, The Pennsylvania State University
Nandita Mani, University of Michigan
Eric Maslowski, University of Michigan

Elizabeth Mengel, Johns Hopkins University
Aaron Purcell, Virginia Tech
Frank Rosa, George Brown College
Katie Rose, University of Notre Dame
Maria Savova, Claremont University Consortium
Jill Sexton, North Carolina State University
Kelcy Shepherd, Amherst College
Jason Smith, Pomona College
Plato Smith II, University of Florida
Michael Thomas, Case Western Reserve University
Elizabeth Waraksa, Association of Research Libraries
Catherine Zabriskie, Brown University
Donna Ziegenfuss, University of Utah

“

LCI changed the way that my cohort and I will think about the problems we are facing in our own institutions and across the higher education sector. At the end of that stimulating week, I headed back to my institution eager to bring it all home, feeling a little dazed, bedazzled, and reenergized. My imagination was stretched to its capacity.

LCI was both a mindful and heartfelt experience—and it felt like a very urgent experience too—because higher education needs new and promising solutions to the challenges that are its future.

—Gayleen Gray, Deputy CIO and Associate Director of Computing and Communications Services, University of Guelph, and participant in 2016 LCI.

An all-class survey covering 2000–2015 revealed that

47% of alumni attributed a career move to their participation in the Institute

51% of alumni attributed a promotion to their participation in the Institute

55% of alumni attributed a salary increase to their participation in the Institute

Departmental Affiliations of Frye/LCI Participants, 2000–2016

Below left: Eric Maslowski, University of Michigan; center: LCI Deans Elliott Shore and Joanne Kossuth with Julie Little of EDUCAUSE; right: Plato Smith, University of Florida, and Jennifer Bowen, University of Rochester. Photos: Christa Williford.

Mellon Fellowships for Dissertation Research in Original Sources

The Mellon Fellowships for Dissertation Research in Original Sources help graduate students in the humanities and related social science fields pursue doctoral research using primary source materials in libraries, archives, museums, and related repositories worldwide.

The exploration and interpretation of original sources—whether paper, potsherds, or born-digital objects—allow us to find meaning in our past and create new knowledge. In recognition of the vital importance of keeping original sources at the heart of knowledge production, CLIR has worked with The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation since 2002 to offer the Mellon Fellowships for Dissertation Research, which offer a unique opportunity for graduate students. Today, new tools for data capture and organization facilitate research that would not have been possible a generation ago. This capability reinforces the need to cultivate a comprehensive understanding of original sources and the institutions that maintain them.

Number of fellowships awarded in 2016: **16**

Number of fellowships awarded since the program's inception: **179**

2016 Mellon Dissertation Fellows

Elham Bakhtary,** The George Washington University
Amir Sher Ali's Lithographic Challenge to the Wahhabi Movement

Alice Baumgartner, Yale University
Fugitives: The Underground Railroad to Mexico

Chelsea Berry, Georgetown University
Poisoned Relations: Medicine, Sorcery, and Poison Trials in the Greater Caribbean, 1690–1850

Eladio Bobadilla, Duke University
From "Wetback Invasion" to "One People without Borders": Mexican Americans and Undocumented Immigrants, 1954–1994

Huiying Chen, University of Illinois at Chicago
Show Me the Way: Culture, Commerce, and Politics of the Road in Eighteenth Century China

Rebecca Egli, University of California, Davis
"The World of Our Dreams": Agricultural Explorers and the Promise of American Science

Jennifer Gaugler, University of California, Berkeley
The Architecture of the Archive, the Museum, and the Heritage Site in Rwanda

Devon Golaszewski, Columbia University
Reproductive Labors: West African Reproductive Expertise and Biomedical Legibility

William Kelly, Rutgers University
Revolución es [Re]construir: Housing Reform in the Cuban Revolution, 1960–1989

Isidora Miranda, University of Wisconsin-Madison
Tagalog Zarzuelas and Musical Nationalism in Early Twentieth-Century Manila, 1902 to 1935

Danya Pilgrim, Yale University
Gastronomic Alchemy: How Black Philadelphia Caterers Transformed Taste into Capital, 1790–1925

Caroline Radesky, University of Iowa
Feeling Historical: Same-Sex Desire and the Politics of History, 1880–1920

Marian Smith, University of Michigan
Reconstructing a Timurid Cosmopolitanism: Abd Allah Hatifi's Timur-nama in the Cultural Production of Early Modern Eurasia

Rory Sykes, Northwestern University
"We Are All Fedayeen": Palestinian National Identity and the Image Archive, 1967–1982

Kena Wani, Duke University
Communication Satellites and the Pursuit of Outer Space in Post-Colonial India, 1960–79

Rachel Welsh, New York University
Proof in the Body: Ordeal, Justice, and the Physical Manifestation of Truth in Medieval Iberia, c. 1050–1300

***Elham Bakhtary is the recipient of the CLIR/Library of Congress Mellon Dissertation Fellowship. The award supports original source research in the Library of Congress's Preservation Research and Testing Division.*

Mellon Fellows Site Visit Locations 2002–2016

In 2016, CLIR awarded 16 fellowships to Ph.D. students whose research on topics ranging from the Underground Railroad to Mexico to Palestinian national identity will take them to five continents and 212 institutions.

CLIR's May 2016 publication, *Terra Cognita: Graduate Students in the Archives*, provides an overview and analysis of the program's first 12 years, based on Fellows' final reports. The volume explores the complex challenges students continue to face as they seek to engage with and understand the rare and unique holdings of libraries, archives, museums, and government agencies across the globe.

The program has given CLIR a perspective from which to assess the changing global landscape for research, mobilize a diverse community of researchers to strengthen ties between the academic and cultural memory sectors, advocate for the significance of original source research to the creation of new knowledge, and awaken the public's curiosity about human history.

“

My experience as a CLIR Mellon Fellow was crucial in developing my research and teaching on modern cross-cultural exchanges in trans-Pacific circuits. . . . I attained skills and creativity in using original sources . . . [and] have incorporated this knowledge and inspiration into my courses on techniques of documentation that make race visible and invisible. Archival sources enable me to recover and teach a forgotten literary history in the Pacific.

— Jang Wook Huh, 2012 Fellow, Visiting Assistant Professor, Department of English, University at Buffalo, SUNY

“

The fellowship offered me the rare opportunity to live and research in Iran at a time when fellowships were hard to come by and strict international sanctions were in place. [It] also opened my eyes to a number of issues and problems that confront librarians, curators, and scholars as they come together toward the common goal of organizing, studying, and preserving cultural patrimony. Such issues have become increasingly pressing today as the Islamic world witnesses unprecedented cultural destruction on the ground.

— Christiane Gruber, 2002 Fellow, Associate Professor of Islamic Art, History of Art Department, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor

CLIR Chief Information Officers Group

(as of 6/30/16)

Suzanne Aber, Trinity College
Param Bedi, Bucknell University
Jim Cubit, Lake Forest College
Jose Dieudonne, Wilson College
Greg Diment, Kalamazoo College
Ronald Griggs, Kenyon College
Lee Hisle, Connecticut College
Rick Holmgren, Allegheny College
Robert Johnson, Rhodes College
Todd Kelley, Carthage College
Roberta Lembke, St. Olaf College
Ravi Ravishanker, Wellesley College
Robert Renaud, Dickinson College
Vicki Sells, Sewanee: The University of the South
Gina Siesing, Bryn Mawr College
Justin Sipher, St. Lawrence University
David Smallen, Hamilton College
Erin Smith, Westminster College
Gene Spencer, Ursinus College
Joanne Steele, Iona College
Bruce Taggart, Lehigh University
Andrew White, Bates College
Alex Wirth-Cauchon, Mount Holyoke College

CLIR Chief Information Officers

Since 2002, CLIR has facilitated a semi-annual forum of directors of organizations that have merged their library and information technology units on the campuses of liberal arts colleges and small universities. At their meetings and through a listserv, members discuss library and computing issues as an integrated whole. They have explored such topics as recent changes in merged organizations, strategic and tactical issues concerning cloud computing, trends in the uses of technology in teaching, and effective ways to provide faculty support.

Digital Library of the Middle East

Throughout 2015 and 2016, CLIR initiated conversations with The Antiquities Coalition and other institutions in the United States and abroad about the feasibility and technical prototyping of a Digital Library of the Middle East (DLME). The DLME is envisioned as a digitally based, internationally shared inventory of cultural artifacts that includes detailed descriptions and images, and confirms objects' ownership and legal status. This information would help determine whether an item of cultural or historical significance offered for sale or being transferred was acquired legally. The DLME could also serve as a resource for teaching and scholarship, and a means by which to engage future generations with this cultural legacy.

CLIR has identified several potential partners in the Middle East, and numerous U.S. research universities have pledged to federate their digital resources pertinent to Middle Eastern culture broadly defined.

The initial phase of this work is supported with planning funds from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, granted in July 2016. The expected outcomes include an assessment of the technical specifications to build the DLME; a registry of related domestic and international digital resources, assets, and projects; and a better understanding of the cultural, political, and technical challenges of working in the region.

Continuous conflict and archaeological looting in the Middle East threaten the preservation of world cultural heritage. The Digital Library of the Middle East aims to create a digitally based, internationally shared inventory of cultural artifacts. Photos: bottom left, RadioKafka/Shutterstock; bottom right, AFP Collection/Getty Images.

AFFILIATES

CLIR has created alliances with a number of institutions and consortia for mutual support of common purposes. The affiliates afford CLIR a broader spectrum of expertise and support to advance its agenda and the opportunity to engage meaningfully with new constituencies.

International Image Interoperability Framework

In October 2015, CLIR became the host institution for the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) Consortium. IIIF is an informal collaboration of prominent libraries and cultural organizations in the United States, United Kingdom, and European Union, including several national libraries. The IIIF community works together to create, test, refine, implement, and promote shared application programming interface specifications for interoperable functionality for digital image repositories. Adoption of IIIF by institutions allows them to transfer and share image pixels, metadata, and annotations across repositories and systems. DLF serves as a professional constituency for IIIF and promotes wider adoption of the framework.

National Digital Stewardship Alliance

On January 1, 2016, the National Digital Stewardship Alliance (NDSA) moved its administrative home from the Library of Congress to DLF. The NDSA is a consortium of more than 200 organizations committed to the long-term preservation of digital information. Its mission is to establish, maintain, and advance the capacity to preserve our nation's digital resources for the benefit of present and future generations. DLF has helped improve processes and workflows for membership participation, launched a new website and communications infrastructure, and revived the annual Digital Preservation conference.

National Institute for Technology in Liberal Education

In July 2015, the National Institute for Technology in Liberal Education (NITLE) moved from Southwestern University to CLIR for a period of re-evaluation. NITLE was established in 2001 to help liberal arts colleges and universities integrate inquiry, pedagogy, and technology. CLIR engaged a team of six consultants to assess the organization and the needs of the liberal arts institutions it has served over its history. The results of the team's investigations were published in August 2016, and an advisory council will recommend next steps.

In addition to periodic reports, CLIR publishes the bimonthly *CLIR Issues* newsletter. CLIR and DLF also publish blog series, which are available at clir.org and diglib.org. For regular updates, follow us on Twitter @CLIRNews, @CLIRDLF, and @CLIRHC, and like us on Facebook.

PUBLICATIONS

July 1, 2015–June 30, 2016

- *Terra Cognita: Graduate Students in the Archives*.
May 2016
- *Innovation, Collaboration, and Models*, Cheryl Oestreicher, editor.
November 2015
- *Building Expertise to Support Digital Scholarship: A Global Perspective*, by
Vivian Lewis, Lisa Spiro, Xuemao Wang, and Jon E. Cawthorne.
October 2015
- *The Process of Discovery: The CLIR Postdoctoral Fellowship Program and the
Future of the Academy*, John C. Maclachlan, Elizabeth A. Waraksa, and
Christa Williford, editors. September 2015
- *The Once and Future Publishing Library* by Ann Okerson and Alex
Holzman. July 2015

RESOURCES and FISCAL MANAGEMENT

Revenue Sources

Expenses

The complete audit for CLIR's financial position as of June 30, 2016 is available at <https://www.clir.org/pubs/annual/2016audit.pdf>.

Statement of Financial Position

as of June 30, 2016

	Unrestricted	Temporary Restricted	Total June 30, 2016
CURRENT ASSETS:			
Cash and cash equivalents	\$936,849	\$3,351,888	\$4,288,737
Investments	8,700	1,133,345	1,142,045
Prepaid expenses	59,445	-	59,445
Accounts receivable	4,689	4,067,711	4,072,400
Total Current Assets	\$1,009,683	\$8,552,944	\$9,562,627
Furniture and equipment, net of accumulated depreciation	\$96,099	\$-	\$96,099
Other assets	29,915	-	29,915
TOTAL ASSETS	\$1,135,697	\$8,552,944	\$9,688,641
CURRENT LIABILITIES:			
Accounts payable	\$283,864	\$-	\$283,864
Capital lease payable	3,591	-	3,591
Accrued expenses	134,187	-	134,187
Total Current Liabilities	\$421,642	\$-	\$421,642
LONG-TERM LIABILITIES:			
Capital lease payable, net of current portion	\$6,950	\$-	\$6,950
TOTAL LIABILITIES	\$428,592	\$-	\$428,592
NET ASSETS	\$707,105	\$8,552,944	\$9,260,049
TOTAL LIABILITIES AND NET ASSETS	\$1,135,697	\$8,552,944	\$9,688,641

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as of June 30, 2016

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Page 4 center: Lizzi Albert

Page 4 bottom left and center: Nikki Ferraiolo

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